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Abstract

This paper presents a simple, neo-classical, method of uncertainty analysis based on the idea that measurement is a procedure that incurs errors. Following a correct interpretation of CIPM Recommendation INC-1 (1980), the method approaches the task of combining random and systematic (deterministic) errors by considering the systematic errors to have been drawn from hypothetical populations whose variances contribute to the law of propagation of error in the usual manner. In Type B evaluation of uncertainty, (which typically relates to systematic components), the method propagates the shapes of the error distributions via the concept of kurtosis and avoids the artificial use of degrees of freedom — which is a known weakness of the procedure of the *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement*. The method has the properties of *internal consistency* and *transferability*, and its coherent theoretical basis promotes *universality*. The method is tuned for simplicity and good performance in simulated measurements. Such simulations give meaning to the idea that a method of uncertainty analysis is to exhibit *validity*.

Keywords: error analysis, frequentist statistics, kurtosis, law of propagation of error, law of propagation of uncertainty

1. Introduction

1 A measurement in the physical sciences is incomplete without a statement of ‘measurement uncertainty’. Some
2 indication must be given of the likely accuracy of the known measured value, y , as a representation of the unknown
3 value of the measurand, Y . However, difficulties arise when we seek to describe or prescribe an appropriate approach
4 to this task: there remain varieties of opinion that support different techniques and invalidate others. The *Guide to the*
5 *Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement* (GUM) [1], first published in 1993, presented a procedure that seems to have
6 widespread acceptance as a practical tool, but — as will be described — there are significant difficulties with the procedure
7 and its apparent conceptual basis. The first two “supplements” to the GUM [2, 3] describe an approach that owes more
8 to concepts of Bayesian statistics than to the classical concepts underlying the GUM procedure, so they do not seek to
9 extend the GUM procedure as much as to supplant it or make it consistent, e.g., [4, Section 3.2]. However, a proposed
10 revision of the GUM based on the Bayesian approach was rejected by stakeholders [5], leaving the future of the GUM
11 and related guidelines uncertain. So it cannot be said that the evaluation of measurement uncertainty has an agreed basis
12 and a concomitant procedure.

13
14 Any coherent approach to the analysis of measurement data must be based on some underlying set of premises,
15 and this must lead to a practical method that is open to proper extension. Therefore, this paper appeals to a formal
16 recommendation said to be the basis of the GUM, and it uses the principle described there to present a modification
17 to the GUM procedure. The result is a method that overcomes the most obvious failings of the GUM procedure while
18 adhering to the largely-uncontroversial classical (or *frequentist*) approach to statistics. In effect, the paper describes what
19 might be called a ‘neo-classical method of error analysis’ for use in the physical sciences. The procedure proposed is as
20 simple as the GUM procedure, and the clarity of its theoretical basis will enable it to be extended. In its earliest form, the
21 procedure was published in 2013 [6]. It was recently summarized at the IMEKO 2021 conference, before appearing in the
22 proceedings of IMEKO 2021 published in this journal [7]. The present paper was prepared in response to an invitation
23 from the journal to describe the method more fully.

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24 *1.1. A watershed for error analysis in measurement*

25 Any satisfactory procedure must somehow treat together the random and non-random contributions to the difference
26 between the measured value y and the true value of the measurand Y , which is the *measurement error*. These contributions
27 may simply be called ‘errors’. Random errors are well handled by classical statistical procedures, but this has not been the
28 case with non-random, so-called ‘systematic’, errors. However, systematic errors are ubiquitous in practical measurement
29 problems and, consequently, the questions of whether and how to combine expressions of random and systematic error
30 have been pertinent for many years.

31 One traditional idea is that each systematic error can be expressed as a pair of limits, with the limits for different
32 errors being added arithmetically [8, 9]. In this way, systematic errors would combine ‘linearly’ through the summation
33 of limits, while random errors would combine ‘in quadrature’ through the familiar summation of variances. The total
34 systematic error from m_s sources would scale with m_s , but the total random error from m_r sources would scale with $\sqrt{m_r}$.
35 There is a lot of intellectual integrity in this position, especially for situations where the constant nature of a systematic
36 error must be taken into account, for example, in routine conformance assessment. However, identifying the limits for
37 each systematic error could be problematic, and the linear increase in the width of the final uncertainty interval with m_s
38 would lead to a large interval: the analysis might be regarded as being unnecessarily conservative.

39 The basic opposing idea is that, much as a variance is associated with a random error by the principles of probability
40 and statistics, so a variance is to be associated with a systematic error by the principles of expert-knowledge and experi-
41 ence, with all the components of error subsequently being summed in quadrature. The sum then scales with $\sqrt{(m_s + m_r)}$,
42 which leads to the quotation of smaller figures of uncertainty, and there becomes less need to specify hard limits from
43 incomplete knowledge of sources of error. This idea, which may be called the ‘randomization of systematic errors’, can
44 be justified in many practical situations by appealing to the idea that clients will encounter a variety of measurement
45 problems to be addressed by a variety of techniques, possibly in different laboratories. So an error that is constant when
46 viewed by the metrologist is somewhat random when experienced by the client: to the client, the metrologist’s fixed setup
47 in a particular type of measurement becomes interpretable as the outcome of a random process [10, Ch. 4]. In this paper,
48 we accept this approach as being appropriate, citing Recommendation INC-1 below as a justification. However, there is
49 not universal agreement about this [8, 9].

50 This idea that variances are to be associated with systematic errors was the considered judgement of a meeting of
51 experts convened by the BIPM in 1980 to address these issues. The conclusions reached by this group were given in a
52 report [11] and were summarized in Recommendation INC-1 (1980) [12][1, 0.7], which has subsequently been referred
53 to as “the CIPM Recommendation INC-1”[13, Introduction]. Correctly interpreted, this recommendation should be seen
54 as a foundation for the modern analysis of measurement error and uncertainty. There at least three reasons for this: (i)
55 it is authoritative, having been formally approved by the CIPM and having been a basis for the method of the GUM [1,
56 0.5,0.7], (ii) it provides a way forward for the development of modern error analysis in measurement, and (iii) it predates
57 controversy in metrology about the relevance of the Bayesian approach to statistical analysis. In particular, it predates
58 the publication of the GUM, which is known to mix classical and Bayesian ideas inappropriately. Thus, there can be
59 no question that Recommendation INC-1 is a greater authority than the GUM as a foundation for our subject. So it is
60 important to understand it correctly.

61 In this paper we take Recommendation INC-1 as a starting point, and subsequently we develop a logically consistent
62 method of uncertainty analysis. The underlying idea is that the ingredients of any analysis are distributions of error asso-
63 ciated with the steps of a measurement procedure. We present a method that implements Recommendation INC-1 while
64 avoiding the criticisms that can be levelled at the *procedure* of the GUM and the *description* given by the GUM, which
65 should be differentiated. The result is a general procedure that is simple, more accurate and more logically satisfying.
66 By replacing the concept of ‘degrees of freedom’ for systematic errors by a concept of distributional shape, we obtain
67 a procedure that can justifiably result in smaller intervals of uncertainty, thus making the procedure more informative or
68 ‘efficient’.

69 *1.2. The structure of the paper*

70 Section 2 presents a number of ideas that form background for the paper. Some of these ideas are generally accepted,
71 while others invite thought and discussion. The concepts described are important, because many of the issues surrounding
72 our subject seem associated with a lack of rigour or a lack of attention to detail. Section 3 expands on the comments given
73 above about Recommendation INC-1, and uses the accompanying report to emphasize its correct interpretation. Section 4
74 presents the new procedure and focuses on its points of difference, which relate to the use of ‘shape information’ in Type B

75 evaluation of uncertainty. Section 5 describes a simulation study carried out to study and enhance the performance of the
76 method. Section 6 contains discussion and conclusions. The method proposed in this paper has already been published in
77 much the same form [6, 7]. For variety and to bring different emphases where appropriate, this paper has been structured
78 differently from those publications. Readers might find some theoretical aspects of the problem described more clearly in
79 the earlier papers.

80 Any argument for the adoption of a new analytical technique is supported by argument against supposed alternatives.
81 Therefore, it is also appropriate to identify major inadequacies in Bayesian approaches, which are currently favoured by
82 the BIPM, e.g., [5]. Accordingly, an appendix planned for this paper has grown into the full paper that follows in this
83 issue [14].

84 2. Background concepts

85 2.1. True values and errors

86 The concept of the ‘true value’ is foundational. The existence of one or more true values is implied in any mathematical
87 equation, so the existence of true values is implied in any symbolic model of measurement: the symbols must stand for
88 things that exist. Some critics of the concept of ‘true value’ point to the notion of ‘definitional uncertainty’, but it is not
89 clear that definitional uncertainty is relevant. For example, the presence of *uncertainty in a sampling procedure* must
90 make it more difficult to obtain a measured value consistent with the definition of the measurand but the presence of
91 *uncertainty in the definition* must make it easier! The two types of uncertainty have opposite effects, so how could they
92 possibly be considered additive components of a single, greater, whole? The concept of definitional uncertainty seems to
93 relate more to doubt about the purpose of the measurement than to the non-existence of a unique ideal result. In summary,
94 it is suggested that definitional uncertainty is something ill-defined that occupies a place *outside* the task of expressing
95 accuracy in measurement and that its presence in a quantitative analysis is, currently, unwarranted and unhelpful.

96 Another simple argument can be raised in support of the notion of the true value. Professional metrologists spend their
97 careers seeking to perfect, as much as is possible, the measurement procedures for which they are responsible. They strive
98 toward the ideal of a perfect measurement, implicitly envisaging the existence of some unattainable ideal result, a result
99 with (legitimately) zero uncertainty. It would make no sense to have such a goal, and then claim that the result would have
100 no unambiguous meaning. Surely this ideal result is another name for the ‘true value’, and vice versa. Without a concept
101 of a true value, the ultimate goal of the metrologist evaporates.

102 As soon as we accept the idea of an ideal result, we find meaning in the terms ‘accuracy’ and ‘error’. It is a fact of
103 life that (in the general case) a measured value y will not be equal to the corresponding true value \underline{Y} . By definition, the
104 difference $y - \underline{Y}$ is known as the ‘measurement error’ e , and it is apparent that this error will be formed from many individual
105 contributions. The task becomes the proper expression of the aggregate of these contributions. These elementary ideas
106 are ‘first principles’ of the analysis of experimental data: without them there is no foundation for an inferential process,
107 no foundation for drawing a conclusion about a physical quantity. In particular, without the concept of a true value there
108 seems to be no assertion for the metrologist to be uncertain about.

109 2.2. Terminology and notation

110 As has been stated, the method of analysis proposed in this paper accords with the essential idea of Recommendation
111 INC-1. However, the language and terminology used here might differ in places. In particular, the term ‘error’
112 describes something quantitative, while the unqualified term ‘uncertainty’ is used to mean something qualitative. When
113 the term ‘uncertainty’ is used to describe something quantitative, it is qualified, as in ‘standard uncertainty’ or ‘interval of
114 uncertainty’.

115 Perhaps in contrast, we can read in the report that accompanied Recommendation INC-1 [11, p.6]:

116 The traditional distinction between “random” and “systematic” uncertainties (or “errors”, as they were often
117 called previously) is purposely avoided here, ...

118 How are we to understand this apparent replacement of the word ‘errors’ by the word ‘uncertainties’? An error is a
119 signed quantity but an uncertainty, if it is a quantity at all, does not have a sign — so the term “errors” in this quotation
120 cannot mean quantities of the type we have just described. Rather, the term “errors” here seems to mean “margins of
121 error”: the concept of ‘error’ can be considered abstract, just as the colloquial idea of ‘uncertainty’ is abstract. So, despite

122 appearances, this quotation has little relevance to the common and proper usage of the quantitative terms ‘the error’ and
123 ‘an error’ maintained throughout this paper.

124 A failure to distinguish between an error and a margin of error would exemplify the kind of loose language that has
125 been detrimental to the development of consensus in this subject. Other examples abound in science. In the author’s
126 original discipline of physics, there is a tendency to fail to differentiate the estimate from the thing estimated, in both
127 language and notation. Similarly, physicists often write ‘determine’ when they mean either ‘estimate’ or ‘determine the
128 estimate of’. Scientists must use different language and notation to differentiate the unknown quantity from its estimate:
129 otherwise we would be writing nonsense like “ $m = m \pm 2u$.”

130 In this paper, we indicate the true value of a quantity using an underlined capital Latin letter, \underline{X}_i or \underline{Y} , and we denote
131 the estimate of it by the corresponding lower-case letter, x_i or y . We reserve a standard capital Latin letter, e.g., X_i , for its
132 important role in statistics of indicating a random variable in a sampling experiment. Our use of \underline{X}_i and \underline{Y} where the GUM
133 uses X_i and Y is an attempt to maintain contact with the notation of the GUM while preserving the statistical meaning
134 of the standard upper-case Latin letter. (Our notation here is the same as in the earlier paper in this journal [7], but it is
135 different from the notation used in the initial presentation of the procedure [6].)

136 There is a subtle difficulty with the word ‘random’. In experimental work, we often speak of ‘random’ and ‘systematic’
137 errors, a random error being one that would have been different on a different occasion. In that sense, the word ‘random’
138 refers to the mode of generation of the error, the *origin* of the error. But the concept of a random entity is foundational in
139 the fields of probability and statistics, where we encounter terms such as ‘random variable’ and ‘random process’. There,
140 the word ‘random’ means that the entity possesses a probability distribution; it is not a number, it is yet to take a number.
141 In that way, the word ‘random’ describes the mathematical *status* of the entity, not the origin of the entity. The difference
142 is important: to the statistician, a random error has the attributes of a random variable, is denoted as such, and it can be
143 regarded as an ‘input’ to a measurement procedure. But to the non-statistical scientist, a random error is an output of a
144 measurement procedure. For this reason, we suggest that the experimental community use the term ‘randomized error’
145 instead. (This is not a trivial matter, because one problem related to the meaning of ‘randomness’ is confusion about
146 the essential concept of a confidence interval. The statistician’s correct idea that “a 95% confidence interval is a random
147 interval with probability 0.95 of enclosing the true value” becomes confused with the incorrect and meaningless notion
148 that a particular realization of the confidence interval is ‘a numerical interval with probability 0.95 of enclosing the true
149 value’.)

150 2.3. *The two tasks of uncertainty analysis*

151 It is both helpful and important to distinguish between two roles for an analysis of measurement uncertainty [15].
152 These roles relate to complementary tasks: the deductive task of propagating the error variance along a chain of mea-
153 surement (which we will call ‘the propagation of variance’) and the non-deductive task of making an inference about the
154 final measurand (which we will call ‘the step of inference’). The propagation of variance is deductive in the sense that
155 knowing the inputs lead to a unique known correct output, i.e., the application of the ‘law of propagation of uncertainty
156 (or error)’ is simply an exercise in deductive mathematics. In contrast, the step of inference is non-deductive, and — if
157 there is a chain of measurement — this step is relevant only to the recipient of the final result. In that step, the principles
158 of statistics, not mathematics, are used to work backwards from the measured value y to make an uncertain statement that
159 the measurand \underline{Y} lies in a numerical interval, say the interval $[y - 1.96u, y + 1.96u]$. We will have much cause to refer to
160 these two tasks separately here.

161 2.4. *Properties of an ideal system*

162 The GUM outlines various properties of an ideal system of uncertainty analysis [1, Clause 0.4], in particular, the
163 properties of *internal consistency* and *transferability*. A system is internally consistent if the results are unchanged when
164 the measurement is decomposed into separate sub-measurements. For example, if the measurand \underline{Y} can be expressed as
165 $\underline{Y} \equiv F_{1,2}(\underline{X}_1, \underline{X}_2)$ where $\underline{X}_1 \equiv F_{3,4}(\underline{X}_3, \underline{X}_4)$ and $\underline{X}_2 \equiv F_{5,6}(\underline{X}_5, \underline{X}_6)$ then it should make no difference if the problem is
166 addressed in this way or by using the corresponding representation $\underline{Y} \equiv F(\underline{X}_3, \underline{X}_4, \underline{X}_5, \underline{X}_6)$. A system exhibits transfer-
167 ability if it enables the measurand \underline{Y} to act as an input to a later measurement, e.g., where the measurand is expressible
168 as $\underline{Z} = F(\underline{Y}, \underline{X})$. A third desirable property is that of *universality*, meaning that the method is applicable in all realistic
169 measurements. Arguably, this can only be an ideal, because there will always be situations where one or other element of
170 the measurement requires a non-standard analysis.

171 A good system will also ‘perform well’, but there is often a lack of discussion of what this is to mean. The most
 172 obvious performance criteria relate to the step of inference. Ideally, uncertainty intervals said to be 95% reliable will
 173 include the true values on at least 95% of occasions and will be narrow (i.e., be informative or statistically efficient). So
 174 the concepts of *validity* and *efficiency* can be added to our list of desiderata.

175 2.5. The GUM procedure and the GUM description

176 The GUM envisages a measurand defined to be a known function of m ‘input’ quantities, $\underline{Y} \equiv F(\underline{X}_1, \dots, \underline{X}_m)$. The
 177 measurand “can be characterized by an essentially unique value” [1, 1.2], and this implies that (at the instants of mea-
 178 surement) each of the m input quantities also has a unique unknown true value. There is a measured value x_i for each \underline{X}_i .
 179 The measured value of \underline{Y} is calculated to be $y \equiv F(x_1, \dots, x_m)$ and the effect on y of a small change in x_i is recorded as
 180 $c_i \equiv \partial y / \partial x_i$, which is calculated either analytically or numerically.

181 There is a figure of ‘standard uncertainty’ u_i provided with each x_i . In the typical Type A evaluation, there will be
 182 n_i individual measured values of \underline{X}_i , say z_1, \dots, z_{n_i} . The combined measured value of \underline{X}_i is equal to the sample mean,
 183 i.e., $x_i \equiv \bar{z} \equiv \sum_{k=1}^{n_i} z_k / n_i$, and u_i^2 is set equal to the best estimate of the parent variance of x_i , i.e., $u_i^2 \equiv s_i^2 / n_i$ where
 184 $s_i^2 \equiv \sum_{k=1}^{n_i} (z_k - \bar{z})^2 / (n_i - 1)$. In contrast, in Type B evaluation, u_i^2 is chosen by a non-statistical method to act as a figure of
 185 effective variance, somewhat in accordance with Recommendation INC-1. Subsequently, in accordance with the ‘law of
 186 propagation or uncertainty’, the GUM advocates that the standard uncertainty to associate with the measured value y be
 187 taken to be $u \equiv \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m c_i^2 u_i^2}$. This fulfils the task we have called the propagation of variance.

188 The GUM envisages that with each u_i there is an associated number of degrees of freedom ν_i . In Type A evaluation,
 189 statistical theory implies that $\nu_i = n_i - 1$. In Type B evaluation, by analogy with a result from classical statistics involving
 190 sampling from a normal distribution, a artificial number of degrees of freedom is defined by $\nu_i = \frac{1}{2} (u_i / \Delta u_i)^2$, where
 191 $(\Delta u_i)^2$ describes doubt about u_i^2 as an estimate of the effective error variance for that component [1, G.4.2]. Then, using
 192 the equation known in metrology as the Welch-Satterthwaite formula [1, G.4.1], which follows from a classical analysis
 193 involving sampling from a normal distribution [16], the effective number of degrees of freedom to associate with the final
 194 standard uncertainty u is

$$\nu \equiv \frac{u^4}{\sum_{i=1}^m c_i^4 u_i^4 / \nu_i}.$$

195 This is taken to mean that a 95% interval of expanded uncertainty for \underline{Y} is $[y - t_{0.975, \nu} u, y + t_{0.975, \nu} u]$, where $t_{0.975, \nu}$ is the
 196 0.975 quantile of Student’s t-distribution with ν degrees of freedom. This helps address the task we have called the step
 197 of inference.

198 Our description of the GUM procedure emphasizes that a number of steps are based on the theory of sampling from
 199 a normal distribution. However, many distributions envisaged in Type B evaluation are non-normal, one popular choice
 200 being ‘rectangular’ or ‘uniform’. Therefore, in this paper and in agreement with others, e.g., [17], we will discard the
 201 artificial degrees-of-freedom concept for Type B evaluation and look for a more satisfactory method of incorporating
 202 non-statistical information into the analysis.

203 The GUM procedure can be followed and applied in practice, and it has standardized much analysis. However, the
 204 text in the GUM that surrounds the procedure has no legitimate statistical interpretation: to the statistically literate reader
 205 seeking to faithfully study and extend the procedure, it is gibberish. Type A evaluation is described in classical frequentist
 206 terms using language and notation found in many texts, where fixed unknowns such as \underline{X}_i and \underline{Y} are non-random. On the
 207 other hand, Type B evaluation is described in a way that makes \underline{X}_i appear to be the subject of a probability statement, i.e.,
 208 to be random, as in a Bayesian statistical analysis. A variance is associated with a Type B analysis but the variance is
 209 attributed to the fixed unknown \underline{X}_i itself, (not to the measurement of it — which is the Type A concept). (Thus, the GUM
 210 description makes a ‘category error’.) Then the numbers of degrees of freedom for Type A and Type B are combined using
 211 a classical equation that would be different if a Bayesian interpretation had been appropriate [18, Appendix B]. Finally,
 212 the resulting procedure is not given a classical interpretation. Instead, the GUM takes the interval obtained to encompass
 213 “a large fraction p of the probability distribution characterized by that result and its combined standard uncertainty” [1,
 214 6.2.2]. By omission, it implies that the long-run frequency property of a confidence-interval procedure does not apply,
 215 and to emphasize this it takes the term “level of confidence” to be more informative than the term “confidence level”!

216 In summary, in may be said that the GUM presents a procedure that owes no allegiance to any of the predominant
 217 views of inference in the statistical community. Accordingly, a noted statistician could write of the *Guide*, i.e. the GUM,
 218 that: [19]

219 there is concern among statisticians that the methods advocated by the *Guide* could prove to be misleading or
220 inaccurate. Widespread acceptance of the paradigm advocated in the *Guide* within the physical science com-
221 munity also has the potential to increase confusion about statistical concepts and thus impede communication
222 between statisticians and nonstatisticians.

223 The BIPM now recognizes the theoretical inconsistency of the GUM, e.g., [20, Section 3], and it has spent many years
224 seeking to revise the GUM, without success [5]. The following paper in this issue [14] contains critical comments on the
225 methodology proposed in that revision. It proves that the approach advocated by the BIPM is logically inconsistent and,
226 hence, bound to fail.

227 3. Recommendation INC-1 and its accompanying report

228 To improve both the procedure of the GUM and the logic behind it, we return to its foundation. In 1980, a meeting of
229 experts was convened by the BIPM to address the joint treatment of random and systematic errors. The recommendation
230 of this group was that the two types of error should, in essence, be regarded in the same way: just as a variance is
231 associated with a random effect, so a variance is to be associated with a systematic effect. This is evident in the report
232 from the meeting (henceforth ‘the report’), which reads [11, Abstract]:

233 The new approach, which abandons the traditional distinction between “random” and “systematic” uncertain-
234 ties, recommends instead the direct estimation of quantities which can be considered as valid approximations
235 to the variances and covariances needed in the general law of “error propagation”.

236 The fact that the experts envisaged the variances of errors is implied in the continued acceptance of the law of propagation
237 of error.

238 Similarly, the report states [11, p.7]:

239 The only viable solution to this problem, it seems, is to follow the prescription contained in the well-known
240 general law of “error propagation”. The essential quantities appearing in this law are the variances (and
241 covariances) of the variables (measurements) involved. This then indicates that, if we look for “useful”
242 measures of uncertainty which can be readily applied to the usual formalism, we have to choose something
243 which can be considered as the best available approximation to the corresponding “standard deviations”.

244 This statement refers to variances of measurements, i.e., the variances of measurement errors. The idea is that, just as in
245 Type A evaluation an estimate x_i is drawn from a population of potential estimates with a variance estimated by u_i^2 , the
246 same applies in Type B evaluation. In accordance with this, we read [11, p.8]:

247 In these approaches it is necessary to make (at least implicitly) some assumption about the underlying pop-
248 ulation. It is left to the personal preference of the experimenter whether this is supposed to be for instance
249 Gaussian or rectangular.

250 The word ‘population’ can have only one interpretation: the experts saw a systematic error as being drawn from some
251 population of errors with a standard deviation that is estimated by the experimenter.

252 Further evidence that the group sought to minimize, not maximize, change to the conceptual basis of error analysis is
253 found near the end of the report. We read [11, p.10]:

254 For applications in industrial metrology it might be useful to remember that the overall uncertainty, provided
255 that the simplifying hypothesis of an underlying normal population is accepted, corresponds in an approxi-
256 mate way to the traditional confidence interval.

257 The report is clear that the process now known as Type B evaluation is to be analogous to the classical procedure now
258 known as Type A evaluation, not *vice versa*. (This author easily obtained a copy of the report [11] from the BIPM website
259 a number of years ago, but it no longer seems available there. It is available from this author on request.)

260 The intention of the group was summarized succinctly in Recommendation INC-1 [12] (‘the recommendation’) which
261 is said to be the foundation of the GUM [1, 0.5]. Points 2, 3 and 4 of the recommendation read [1, 0.7]:

- 262 2. The components in category A are characterized by the estimated variances, s_i^2 , (or the estimated “standard de-
 263 viations” s_i) and the number of degrees of freedom, ν_i . Where appropriate, the estimated covariances should be
 264 given.
- 265 3. The components in category B should be characterized by quantities u_j^2 , which may be considered as approximations
 266 to the corresponding variances, the existence of which is assumed. The quantities u_j^2 may be treated like variances
 267 and the quantities u_j like standard deviations. Where appropriate, the covariances should be treated in a similar
 268 way.
- 269 4. The combined uncertainty should be characterized by the numerical value obtained by applying the usual method
 270 for the combination of variances. The combined uncertainty and its components should be expressed in the form of
 271 “standard deviations”.

272 Point 2 recommends continuation of the accepted way of treating statistical errors by the principles of classical data-
 273 analysis. Also, Point 3 outlines the step, not at that time accepted, of associating analogous figures of variance with non-
 274 statistical errors. The phrase “the existence of which is assumed” indicates that, for the j th effect, the writers envisage
 275 a hypothetical population of various entities with variance approximately u_j^2 . Therefore, points 2 and 3 describe the
 276 specification of figures of variances to be treated on equal footing in their combination according to the law of propagation
 277 of error, which is described in Point 4. The parallel presentation of Points 2 and 3 and the phrase “the usual method for
 278 the combination of variances” in Point 4 show that the variances are to be the same in nature; they are both to be variances
 279 of errors or measurements, i.e., measured values.

280 These ideas are straightforward. However, arguably, the conciseness of the recommendation led to a problem. The
 281 GUM seems to take Point 3 to suggest that a variance could be describe the fixed quantity measured, \underline{X}_i , as in a Bayesian
 282 analysis. Thus, the writers of the GUM, in effect, misinterpreted the foundational recommendation on which the GUM
 283 is said to be based. This error is also evident in publications associated with Supplements 1 and 2 to the GUM and
 284 in the proposed revision of the GUM. For example, in presenting material that “represents work of JCGM/WG1” [21,
 285 Acknowledgements], Bich, Cox and Harris write “The basis of the GUM is Recommendation INC1” and “The GUM
 286 is founded on probability theory where information regarding the quantities of concern is characterized by probability
 287 distributions” [21, Sections 1 and 4]. The ‘quantities’ referred to are constants. If Recommendation INC-1 is interpreted
 288 correctly, so that it becomes a (quasi-)frequentist recommendation, then these statements are contradictory.

289 3.1. The corresponding model

290 As has already been stated in Section 1.1, Recommendation INC-1 must be regarded as a greater authority than the
 291 GUM. So we now make the ideas of the recommendation concrete by incorporating them into a mathematical model of a
 292 measurement procedure. The model implied, and its expression in GUM formalism, are as follows.

293 The measurand \underline{Y} is defined to be a known function of a number of ‘input quantities’,

$$294 \underline{Y} \equiv F(\underline{X}_1, \dots, \underline{X}_m). \quad (1)$$

295 Each of the $m + 1$ quantities in this equation is understood to have an “essentially unique” unknown true value that is
 296 approximated as best as possible in some appropriate measurement or estimation procedure. The estimate of \underline{X}_i obtained
 is x_i , and the corresponding estimate of \underline{Y} is then defined to be

$$297 y \equiv F(x_1, \dots, x_m). \quad (2)$$

298 The estimate x_i of \underline{X}_i is understood to have been generated by a (real or hypothetical) process that, on repetition, would
 299 produce a distribution of values with mean \underline{X}_i and some variance σ_i^2 . In other words, x_i is understood to have been drawn
 from a distribution with mean \underline{X}_i and variance σ_i^2 . This relationship can be symbolized by

$$300 x_i \leftarrow (\underline{X}_i, \sigma_i^2), \quad (3)$$

301 where ‘ \leftarrow ’ can be read as ‘is drawn from’. For simplicity here, we assume the usual case where each x_i is drawn
 independently.

302 The analogous parent distribution of y is related to the parent distributions of x_1, \dots, x_m and to the function F . In
 303 practice, F is adequately represented by the *sensitivity coefficients* c_1, \dots, c_m where, as in the GUM procedure,

$$c_i \equiv \left. \frac{\partial F(x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}, z, x_{i+1}, \dots, x_m)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=x_i}. \quad (4)$$

304 More specifically, because the *linear approximation* to F will typically be adequate, the parent distribution of y will have
 305 mean approximately equal to \underline{Y} and variance approximately equal to $\sum_{i=1}^m c_i^2 \sigma_i^2$. Each σ_i^2 has a known estimate u_i^2 . It is
 306 then apparent that we can make the approximation

$$y \stackrel{\text{approx.}}{\leftarrow} (\underline{Y}, u^2) \quad (5)$$

307 where

$$u^2 \equiv \sum_{i=1}^m c_i^2 u_i^2, \quad (6)$$

308 i.e., that we can regard y as having been drawn from a distribution with mean approximately equal to \underline{Y} and variance
 309 approximately equal to u^2 . Therefore, it is appropriate to take the figure u to be the ‘standard uncertainty’ in y as the
 310 measured value of \underline{Y} .

311 For any i , the figure u_i is determined either by a statistical method, (Type A evaluation), or by a non-statistical method,
 312 (Type B evaluation). In Type A evaluation involving n_i repeated observations drawn from a distribution with variance δ_i^2 ,
 313 the variance σ_i^2 is real and is equal to δ_i^2/n . Then an unbiased estimate of σ_i^2 is s_i^2/n_i where s_i^2 is the ‘sample variance’,
 314 and the number of degrees of freedom associated with this estimate is $n_i - 1$. So Type A evaluation involves recording the
 315 figures

$$u_i^2 \equiv s_i^2/n_i \approx \sigma_i^2 \quad \nu_i \equiv n_i - 1. \quad (\text{Type A}) \quad (7)$$

316 The figure ν_i is usually used to index a t-distribution. This implies that the parent distribution of x_i is being treated as
 317 normal. Thus, in Type A evaluation, an expression consistent with (3) but with more detail is

$$x_i \leftarrow N(\underline{X}_i, \sigma_i^2), \quad (\text{Type A}) \quad (8)$$

318 where N indicates that the distribution is normal.

319 In contrast, in Type B evaluation, the parent distribution of x_i represents a hypothetical population of potential mea-
 320 sured values, so σ_i^2 is a hypothetical quantity. Based on non-statistical expert knowledge, an estimate u_i^2 of σ_i^2 is obtained.
 321 So Type B evaluation involves recording the quantity

$$u_i^2 \approx \sigma_i^2. \quad (\text{Type B}) \quad (9)$$

322 The form of the distribution will be assumed, but it is not necessarily normal. In both Type A and Type B evaluation, the
 323 figure u_i^2 is understood to be an unbiased estimate of σ_i^2 , so u^2 is interpreted as an unbiased estimate of the variance of the
 324 overall measurement error. Recording u^2 in (6) therefore fulfils the task of the propagation of variance.

325 So Recommendation INC1 leads to a measurement procedure that follows (1)–(9). The model given by these equations
 326 represents the content of the recommendation and the conclusions expressed in the report. The novel contribution of the
 327 recommendation to the model is found in the generality of equation (3), which is assumed to apply for all components of
 328 uncertainty, not just for those that are amenable to statistical analysis, i.e., not just for those subject to Type A evaluation.
 329 The model can be seen to be consistent with the material quoted from the report and with much of the GUM procedure
 330 described in Section 2.5. The assumption of a hypothetical population of errors in Type B evaluation means that the
 331 model cannot legitimately be described as classical. However, because the method maintains the frequentist approach to
 332 statistical analysis and because Type B evaluation is constructed to be consistent with Type A evaluation, the adjective
 333 *neo-classical* seems appropriate.

324 3.2. The views of others

335 Recommendation INC-1 outlines a neo-classical approach to error analysis in the physical sciences. Similarly, there
 336 are later publications that view the task that way, e.g., [22, 23, 24]. However, the BIPM — through the Joint Committee

337 for Guides in Metrology (JCGM) — has proposed that uncertainty analysis be conducted using a Bayesian approach. In
 338 arguing for this, Bich [4] writes:

339 Although frequentism is a perfectly respectable position, it has been proved unfit to accommodate the case of
 340 uncertainties originated by systematic effects. As a consequence, the JCGM decided that there was no valid
 341 alternative to the Bayesian approach.

342 Bich does not provide any reference to any proof that the frequentist position is not fit for this purpose. In fact, correct
 343 interpretation of Recommendation INC-1 provides such a valid frequentist alternative. Therefore, physical scientists who
 344 enjoy a respectable position need not abandon the principles of their reasoning. In contrast, those who take a Bayesian
 345 point of view will find proof of their logical error in the following paper [14]. For a Bayesian position to be logically
 346 defensible, the arguments given there must be shown to be faulty.

347 4. A procedure for the evaluation of measurement uncertainty

348 In this section, we use the model described in (1)–(9) to develop a general procedure for the evaluation of uncertainty
 349 in physical measurements. As would be hoped, the procedure is very similar to the procedure of the GUM. The differences
 350 are found in (a) the meaning of the auxiliary figure recorded for Type B evaluation, (b) the way this figure is combined
 351 with the number of degrees of freedom in Type A evaluation, and (c) the function subsequently used to determine the
 352 width of an uncertainty interval. The procedure is as simple as the procedure of the GUM, and it is equivalent when all
 353 components of error are of Type A. However, the *description* of the procedure is markedly different from the description
 354 given by the GUM because it avoids mixing statistical paradigms, it employs the traditional language of true value and
 355 error, and it uses more-standard statistical notation. For convenience, the terms ‘Type A error’ and ‘Type B error’ are used
 356 to refer to components of the measurement error assessed by Type A and Type B methods. This does not imply that the
 357 two types of error have different statuses: it is merely a matter of choosing simple language.

358 4.1. Representation in terms of random variables and errors

359 Our classical focus means that it is appropriate to identify *the random variables* relevant to the measurement process.
 360 This enables us to correctly describe measurement as a procedure. So we let X_i denote the entity that (i) at the beginning
 361 of the procedure had the potential to take any value in some range but (ii) eventually took the value x_i . Thus, X_i denotes
 362 the observable random variable that had a probability distribution centred on \underline{X}_i and was realized in the known number x_i .
 363 (In statistical parlance, X_i is an *estimator* of \underline{X}_i and x_i is the corresponding *estimate*. An estimator can be thought of as a
 364 rule or procedure for obtaining an estimate.) Likewise, Y denotes the observable random variable that was realized as the
 365 measured value y . Thus, the measurement is described by the procedure

$$366 Y = F(X_1, \dots, X_m), \quad (10)$$

367 (and the probability distributions of Y and X_i are the distributions previously referred to as the *parent distributions* of y and
 368 x_i). The parallel between (10) and (1) is clear, but the equations involve different types of entity. Equation (1) describes a
 369 relationship between unknown constants, but (10) describes a relationship between estimators of these unknown constants:
 it represents the physical processes of the measurement.

Similarly, we let E_i denote the unobservable random variable realized in the unknown error $e_i \equiv x_i - \underline{X}_i$. Thus, the
 procedure of measuring or estimating the constant \underline{X}_i is described by the equation

$$X_i = \underline{X}_i + E_i,$$

370 where X_i and E_i are random variables with means \underline{X}_i and 0, both having variance σ_i^2 . Using a standard statistical notation,
 371 we write

$$E_i \sim N(0, \sigma_i^2) \quad (\text{Type A}) \quad (11)$$

372 for Type A errors and

$$E_i \sim (0, \sigma_i^2) \quad (\text{Type B}) \quad (12)$$

373 for Type B errors. Here ‘ \sim ’ means ‘has the distribution (of)’. We can also write

$$E_i \perp E_j \quad (13)$$

374 to indicate that the random variables E_i and E_j are independent. Therefore, the probabilistic or statistical model of the
375 measurement procedure is given jointly by the equation

$$Y = F(\underline{X}_1 + E_1, \dots, \underline{X}_m + E_m), \quad (14)$$

376 by (11)–(13), and by any information about the shapes of the distributions of the Type B errors.

377 The propagation of variance is the deductive calculation of the variance of Y from this model, while the step of
378 inference is the non-deductive process of reasoning backwards from the observations x_1, \dots, x_m to infer values of \underline{Y} that
379 are in keeping with these data. Both tasks are facilitated by writing (14) as a Taylor’s series expansion

$$Y = F(\underline{X}_1, \dots, \underline{X}_m) + \sum_{i=1}^m E_i \frac{\partial F(\underline{X}_1, \dots, \underline{X}_m)}{\partial \underline{X}_i} + \text{higher order terms},$$

which suggests making the approximation

$$Y \approx \underline{Y} + \sum_{i=1}^m c_i E_i,$$

where c_i is the sensitivity coefficient defined in (4). Then the propagation of variances is carried out by recognizing that
the variance of the overall measurement error $E \equiv Y - \underline{Y}$ is

$$\text{var}[E] \approx \sum_{i=1}^m c_i^2 \sigma_i^2$$

380 and by representing σ_i^2 by some figure u_i^2 . The result is the figure of variance u^2 given by (6).

381 The step of inference is carried out using the auxiliary data, which for Type A evaluations are numbers of degrees of
382 freedom (see Section 4.2) and for Type B evaluations are primarily measures of distributional shape (see Sections 4.3 and
383 4.5).

384 4.2. Type A evaluation: the propagation of variance and degrees of freedom

385 In Type A evaluation, the square of the standard uncertainty u_i^2 is to be the best unbiased estimate of the variance of
386 the component of error. In the archetypal evaluation involving n_i repeated individual measurements z_1, \dots, z_{n_i} of \underline{X}_i , the
387 measured value is chosen to be the sample mean, i.e., $x_i \equiv \bar{z} \equiv \sum_{k=1}^{n_i} z_k / n_i$, and u_i^2 is chosen to be the best estimate of the
388 parent variance of the sample mean, i.e., $u_i^2 = s_i^2 / n_i$ where $s_i^2 \equiv \sum_{k=1}^{n_i} (z_k - \bar{z})^2 / (n_i - 1)$. The concept of $n_i - 1$ degrees of
389 freedom relates to the accuracy of this estimate.

390 If we considered the set of Type A errors in isolation, summed over the relevant subset of the set of indices $\{1, \dots, m\}$
391 and indicated this by A, we would calculate the square of the corresponding standard uncertainty to be

$$u_A^2 = \sum_A c_i^2 u_i^2 \quad (15)$$

392 and (assuming normality) the effective number of degrees of freedom to be

$$\nu \equiv \frac{u_A^4}{\sum_A c_i^4 u_i^4 / \nu_i}. \quad (16)$$

393 This treatment of Type A errors is exactly the same as in the GUM.

394 For (15) to be an unbiased estimate of the overall error variance, it is not necessary for the distributions of the errors to
395 be normal. However, normality is assumed when the number of degrees of freedom (16) is used to index a t-distribution.
396 So the archetypal Type A evaluation assumes normality for the distribution of the error E_i .

397 *4.3. Type B evaluation: the propagation of variance and kurtosis*

398 In Type B evaluation there is often less justification for the idea that E_i is normal. This is one reason why the GUM's
 399 concept of an effective number of degrees of freedom in Type B evaluation should be discarded. So we now look for an
 400 alternative means of providing auxiliary information about a Type B error E_i .

401 For the moment, let us imagine that the estimates of variance in (9) were exact. Then the distributions would be
 402 assumed fully known, and the propagation of these distributions could, in principle, be made exact: the addition of
 403 variances could be replaced by the convolution of probability density functions, and the result obtained would be exact
 404 (notwithstanding the effect of non-linearity). However, such 'propagation of error distributions' seems impractical because
 405 of the apparent need to store and transfer whole 'curves' of information, not just a few summary figures. So, we will now
 406 look to augment the estimate of variance with information about a single central moment of higher order. (Of course,
 407 this presupposes that we wish to improve upon the basic propagation of variance estimates and the subsequent use of the
 408 simple ' $\pm 2u$ ' rule. There are many experimentalists who would be content with that approach.)

409 Almost all distributions used to model errors are symmetric, so the next moment of interest is the fourth central mo-
 410 ment, μ_4 . The fourth central moment of E_i has the dimension of E_i^4 , so normalization is required to obtain a dimensionless
 411 figure that helps describe the basic shape of the distribution. The result is the figure of excess kurtosis, $\gamma \equiv \mu_4/\sigma^4 - 3$,
 412 which takes simple values for certain forms of distribution. Figure 1 shows the probability density functions of the Laplace
 413 distribution (double exponential), the normal distribution, the isosceles triangular distribution, the uniform distribution and
 414 the arc-sine distribution, and indicates the values of excess kurtosis for these symmetric variables. The distributions are
 415 standardized, i.e., translated and scaled to have mean 0 and standard deviation 1, but this does not affect the figures of
 416 kurtosis, which are functions of the shape of the distribution only.

417 The names 'excess kurtosis' and 'coefficient of excess' refer to the fact that γ measures the kurtosis in excess of
 418 the value for the normal distribution. For a normal distribution, the actual kurtosis is 3 and γ is set equal to zero by
 419 construction. The terminology varies in the literature, but for simplicity we will now use the term 'kurtosis' to refer to the
 420 excess quantity, γ .

421 So the kurtosis γ_i of a Type B error E_i is zero if the distribution of E_i is normal and is negative if the distribution
 422 has lighter tails, i.e., if the probability density function is 'blunter' in appearance. Because many Type B errors will be
 423 blunter than normal, the quantile that is eventually appropriate for the half-width of an interval will often be smaller than
 424 the quantile of the standard normal distribution. The interval will then be shorter and hence more informative. This is one
 425 of the properties of Type B errors exploited in the procedure.

426 Our analysis involves the exact propagation of the *cumulants* of random variables, e.g., [?]. Like an r th moment, the
 427 r th cumulant of a random variable X has the dimension of X^r . The second cumulant is the variance $\kappa_2 = \sigma^2$ and the fourth
 428 cumulant is $\kappa_4 = \mu_4 - 3\kappa_2^2$. When independent random variables are added, the cumulants of the same order are added. It
 429 follows that when there are several independent Type B errors with multipliers or weights $\{c_i\}$ and unbiased estimates of
 430 variances $\{u_i^2\}$, the resulting weighted sum of these errors $\sum_B c_i E_i$ has unbiased estimate of variance

$$u_B^2 = \sum_B c_i^2 u_i^2 \quad (17)$$

431 and when the distributions of the errors have kurtoses $\{\gamma_i\}$ (and each u_i^2 is exact) the resulting sum has kurtosis [25, sec.
 432 2][10, sec. 7.3]

$$\gamma = \frac{\sum_B c_i^4 \gamma_i u_i^4}{u_B^4}. \quad (18)$$

433 Equation (17) is, of course, analogous to (15). Equation (18) shows how the kurtosis of the sum is related to the kurtoses
 434 and scales of the components. It allows the propagation of shape information when independent symmetric random
 435 variables are summed. The effects of the errors in the u_i^2 estimates on the numerator and denominator of (18) will almost
 436 cancel, so we shall proceed on the basis that the figure γ obtained from (18) is exact.

437 *4.4. Combining the components: the key to the new procedure*

438 The variance of the total error is estimated to be $u^2 = u_A^2 + u_B^2$. This leads to the standard result (6), which is sufficient
 439 for the task of propagating variance. However, it remains to combine v and γ in such a way as to lead to an accurate

Figure 1: Symmetric probability density functions with different amounts of kurtosis γ . Dotted line - Laplace (double exponential). Thin solid lines - normal and uniform. Dashed line - isosceles triangular. Thick solid line - arc-sine. (The distributions shown are standardized, i.e., are translated to have mean 0 and standard deviation 1. For clarity, the upper tail of the Laplace distribution is obscured).

440 interval, i.e., an accurate procedure. This is accomplished by recognizing that (18) has the same form as the equation

$$\frac{1}{\nu} = \frac{\sum_A c_i^4 \frac{1}{\nu_i} u_i^4}{u_A^4},$$

441 which is a re-expression of (16). It follows that, for a constant multiplier h yet to be determined, a simple means of treating
 442 the two types of error together is to set $\tau_i = 1/\nu_i$ for a Type A error and to set $\tau_i = h\nu_i$ for a Type B error, so that (16) and
 443 (18) can be written in the same form as

$$\tau_A = \frac{\sum_A \tau_i c_i^4 u_i^4}{u_A^4} \quad \text{and} \quad \tau_B = \frac{\sum_B \tau_i c_i^4 u_i^4}{u_B^4}.$$

444 Equivalently, $\tau_A u_A^4 = \sum_A \tau_i c_i^4 u_i^4$ and $\tau_B u_B^4 = \sum_B \tau_i c_i^4 u_i^4$. On summing, we find that we can write $\tau u^4 = \sum_{i=1}^m \tau_i c_i^4 u_i^4$ where

$$\tau \equiv \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \tau_i c_i^4 u_i^4}{u^4}. \quad (19)$$

445 This gives the effective, combined, value of τ .

446 Equation (19) offers a simple and appropriate means of combining the different types of auxiliary information that
447 arise in Type A and Type B evaluations. A Type A evaluation is associated with a positive value of τ_i and with a ‘coverage
448 factor’ larger than that for a standard normal distribution, while a Type B evaluation can involve a negative value of τ_i and
449 a smaller coverage factor. Consequently, a suitable value of h leads to a combined expression (19) that can help balance the
450 effects. Then, after judicious choice of coverage-factor functions $k_{95}(\tau)$ and $k_{99}(\tau)$, the intervals $[y - k_{95}(\tau)u, y + k_{95}(\tau)u]$
451 and $[y - k_{99}(\tau)u, y + k_{99}(\tau)u]$ can be taken as 95% and 99% intervals of uncertainty for the measurand \underline{Y} . The method will
452 be as simple as the method of the GUM and will be more theoretically satisfactory. If the choices of h , $k_{95}(\tau)$ and $k_{99}(\tau)$
453 are made well then the method might also be expected to have superior performance.

454 4.5. Type B evaluation with uncertain scale

455 We now address a complication that can arise in Type B evaluation. The GUM envisages a situation where the
456 metrologist is uncertain about u_i and expresses this in a statement such as u_i is “reliable to 25%” [1, G.4.2]. In our
457 implementation of Recommendation INC-1, this describes doubt about the scale of the hypothetical distribution of the
458 Type B error E_i . So now we indicate how this situation can be accommodated.

459 The presence of uncertainty about the scale factor of a Type B error would be expected to increase the width of an
460 associated interval. However, we do not wish to adjust u_i because — for the propagation of variance — the square of
461 the figure of standard uncertainty is to remain an unbiased estimate of the measurement variance. So, instead, we will
462 represent this broadening of an interval by an appropriate increase in the accompanying figure of kurtosis. Our suggestion
463 is that if a Type B error has proposed kurtosis γ_i^* and has estimated standard deviation u_i deemed reliable to $100\delta_i\%$ then
464 the error be attributed an effective kurtosis

$$\gamma_i = (1 + \delta_i^2)^{12} (\gamma_i^* + 3) - 3. \quad (20)$$

465 The appropriate value τ_i would then be $\tau_i = h\gamma_i$. In this way, non-normality and scale-uncertainty are able to be repre-
466 sented jointly and simultaneously in the single auxiliary figure τ_i .

467 The argument leading to this adjustment is described in the Appendix. It is somewhat informal, but it appeals to the
468 basic idea of ‘fiducial’ inference, which is that the distribution of an estimator dependent on a parameter can be inverted
469 to form the fiducial distribution of the parameter given the numerical estimate. This adjustment differs from that found in
470 the earliest presentation of the method [6, Sec. 2.3], where δ_i was taken to be the half-width of a uniform distribution and
471 where adjustments were made to the estimates of both variance and kurtosis. As shown in the Appendix, the use of (20)
472 is based, first, on the idea that u_i^2 is to remain an unbiased estimate of σ_i^2 (which is implied in Recommendation INC-1)
473 and, second, on the idea that δ_i describes the relative standard uncertainty attributable to u_i (which is found in the GUM).

474 This part of the proposed procedure involves the idea of ‘being unsure about a hypothetical quantity’. This idea seems
475 to me to be logically dubious. If the hypothetical distribution in some sense represents the metrologist’s belief about the
476 appropriate error distribution then that belief would be represented directly in a single distribution with known scale and
477 shape, (not in a two-stage process that is constrained to leave the variance unchanged). The initial figures of u_i^2 and γ_i^*
478 would have a clearer meaning and would not need any adjustment. So it is questionable whether this step of the procedure
479 should be required at all. If this criticism is accepted, then the idea in Recommendation INC-1 that u_i^2 is merely an
480 estimate of σ_i^2 in a Type B evaluation will be replaced by the idea that u_i^2 is equal to σ_i^2 , and equation (9) will become
481 ‘ $u_i^2 = \sigma_i^2$ ’.

482 4.6. Remaining detail

483 The multiplier h and the functions $k_{95}(\tau)$ and $k_{99}(\tau)$ are to be chosen for accuracy, efficiency and simplicity. Set
484 $p^* \equiv 1 - (1 - 0.01p)/2$, so $p^* = 0.975$ and $p^* = 0.995$ for $p = 95$ and $p = 99$. A number of stipulations seem reasonable.

- 485 1. If $\tau \geq 0$ then $k_p(\tau)$ is equal to the p^* quantile of the t-distribution with $1/\tau$ degrees of freedom.
- 486 2. So if $\tau = 0$ then $k_p(\tau)$ is equal to the p^* quantile of the standard normal distribution.
- 487 3. If $\tau = -1.2h$ then $k_p(\tau)$ is equal to the p^* quantile of the standardized uniform distribution.
- 488 4. If $\tau = -1.5h$ then $k_p(\tau)$ is equal to the p^* quantile of the standardized arc-sine distribution.
- 489 5. The method accommodates any value of τ between $-1.5h$ and 1.
- 490 6. The function $k_p(\tau)$ is continuous.

491 Stipulation 1 means that the procedure will reproduce the result of the GUM procedure when all components of uncertainty
 492 are evaluated by the usual Type A technique. Stipulation 3 means that the result will be accurate when one rectangular
 493 Type B component is dominant, while Stipulation 4 means that the method will be applicable in the unlikely situation
 494 where one arc-sine Type B component is dominant. Stipulations 5 and 6 describe reasonable properties of a system that is
 495 intended for practical use. The remaining flexibility in function $k_p(\tau)$ is associated with the choice of h , the interpolation
 496 between the prescribed values at $\tau = 0$ and $\tau = -1.2h$ and the extrapolation of the function to $\tau = -1.5h$.

497 With regard to performance, the choice of h is not as important as might first be thought. It only affects performance
 498 when both Type A and Type B errors are present, and its effects are of second order. A suitable choice is $h = 0.01$.
 499 The choices for the associated functions $k_{95}(\tau)$ and $k_{99}(\tau)$ are given below in (25) and (26). There is nothing theoretical
 500 about the detail of these equations: each right-hand side is simply an empirical approximation in the form of a rational
 501 polynomial. Stipulation 1 is met (approximately) because the lower branches of the equations give close approximations
 502 to the 0.975 and 0.995 quantiles of the t-distribution with $\nu = 1/\tau$ degrees of freedom. Similarly, Stipulations 2, 3 and 4 are
 503 met because the upper branches give close approximations to the 0.975 and 0.995 quantiles of a standardized symmetric
 504 beta distribution with kurtosis $\gamma = \tau/h = 100\tau$; the normal, uniform and arc-sine distributions being symmetric beta
 505 distributions with $\gamma = 0, -1.2, -1.5$, respectively. Figure 2 shows the functions $k_{95}(\tau)$ and $k_{99}(\tau)$ and the quantiles $t_{0.975,1/\tau}$
 506 and $t_{0.995,1/\tau}$ for $\tau = 0.05, 0.1, \dots, 1$. Figure 3 focuses on the region with $\tau \approx 0$.

Figure 2: The functions $k_{95}(\tau)$ and $k_{99}(\tau)$ for $-0.015 \leq \tau \leq 1$ and the quantiles $t_{0.975,1/\tau}$ and $t_{0.995,1/\tau}$ for $\tau = 0.05, 0.1, \dots, 1$

507 4.7. The full procedure

508 This section gives a concise description of the full analytical procedure. It is written in terms of actual data, not
 509 random variables.

510 The measurand is defined by $\underline{Y} = F(\underline{X}_1, \dots, \underline{X}_m)$, where F is a known function and $\underline{X}_1, \dots, \underline{X}_m$ are the unique
 511 unknown values of estimable quantities. If x_1, \dots, x_m are the estimates of $\underline{X}_1, \dots, \underline{X}_m$ then the measured value
 512 of \underline{Y} is taken to be

$$y = F(x_1, \dots, x_m). \quad (21)$$

513 Suppose u_1, \dots, u_m are the figures of standard uncertainty associated with x_1, \dots, x_m . The reliabilities of
 514 u_1, \dots, u_m are expressed in auxiliary figures τ_1, \dots, τ_m that are obtained in a number of ways.

Figure 3: The functions $k_{95}(\tau)$ and $k_{99}(\tau)$ for $\tau \approx 0$

- 515 • If u_i has been calculated in a previous measurement involving this methodology then τ_i will have been
516 stored during that analysis.
- 517 • If u_i^2 is the unbiased estimate of the (parent) variance of the error $x_i - \underline{X}_i$ based on averaging a sample
518 of n_i measurements then $\tau_i = 1/(n_i - 1)$.
- 519 • If u_i^2 is an unbiased estimate of the variance of a (parent) distribution attributed to the error $x_i - \underline{X}_i$ by
520 non-statistical means then $\tau_i = 0.01\gamma_i$ where γ_i is the (excess) kurtosis of that distribution, as indicated
521 in Figure 1. In this situation, γ_i might be obtained by assuming a distribution with kurtosis γ_i^* and with
522 a standard deviation u_i estimated to be “reliable to 100 δ_i %”. If this is the case then we set

$$\tau_i = 0.01 \left(1 + \delta_i^2\right)^{12} (\gamma_i^* + 3) - 3. \quad (22)$$

523 Define the sensitivity coefficient $c_i = \partial y / \partial x_i$, as in (4). If the errors or ‘uncertainties’ in the x_i estimates
524 are incurred independently then the standard uncertainty to be associated with y as the measured value of \underline{Y}
525 is

$$u = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m c_i^2 u_i^2} \quad (23)$$

526 and the auxiliary figure to accompany u is

$$\tau = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \tau_i c_i^4 u_i^4}{u^4}. \quad (24)$$

527 The figures y , u and τ given by (21), (23) and (24) are used to represent \underline{Y} in any subsequent measurement
528 where \underline{Y} plays the role of an input quantity.

529 If \underline{Y} is the object of inference then 95% and 99% intervals of expanded uncertainty for \underline{Y} are $[y -$

530 $k_{95}(\tau)u$, $y + k_{95}(\tau)u$] and $[y - k_{99}(\tau)u$, $y + k_{99}(\tau)u$] where

$$k_{95}(\tau) = \begin{cases} \frac{1.960 + 86.772 \tau + 5.276 \tau^2}{1 + 42.155 \tau + 449.752 \tau^2} & -0.015 \leq \tau < 0 \\ \frac{1.960 + 1.491 \tau + 1.381 \tau^2 + 1.864 \tau^3}{1 - 0.473 \tau} & 0 \leq \tau \leq 1 \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

531 and

$$k_{99}(\tau) = \begin{cases} \frac{2.576 + 189.361 \tau + 4380.163 \tau^2}{1 + 59.309 \tau + 1778.923 \tau^2} & -0.015 \leq \tau < 0 \\ \frac{2.576 + 3.131 \tau + 3.095 \tau^2 + 10.777 \tau^3}{1 - 0.780 \tau + 0.075 \tau^2 + 0.012 \tau^3} & 0 \leq \tau \leq 1. \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

532 The regular calculation of such intervals is designed to bound the true values of the measurands on approxi-
533 mately 95 and 99 percent of occasions \square

534 The procedure can be called the τ procedure ('tau procedure'). It is primarily intended as a modification of the proce-
535 dure of the GUM for the explicit accommodation of Type B errors drawn from non-normal distributions. Equation (22)
536 enables the method to incorporate the idea of error or uncertainty in the figure of variance for the Type B error. Equa-
537 tion (23) is the law of propagation of uncertainty with uncorrelated errors, while (24) replaces the 'Welch-Satterthwaite
538 formula' described in Section 2.5, which would be recovered by setting $\nu_i = 1/\tau_i$ for all i . Equations (25) and (26) give
539 appropriately small 'coverage factors' when $\tau < 0$ and they remove the need for tables of the t -distribution when $\tau > 0$.

540 5. Performance assessment

541 To assess the quality of any analytical method we must know what the method is intended to achieve. As implied
542 in Section 2.4, our goal is to obtain a method of analysis that is internally consistent, transferable, universal, valid and
543 efficient. Like the method of the GUM, the proposed method satisfies the requirements of internal consistency and
544 transferability. Also, with its stronger theoretical basis, the proposed procedure can be said to be more extensible and,
545 hence, more universal than the GUM procedure: see, for example, the way in which classical principles can allow for
546 dependent components of error [16] or multivariate measurands [26]. So the remainder of this section considers the
547 concepts of validity and efficiency, which are the main concepts of practical performance found in classical statistical
548 inference.

549 In our context, the statistical inference is the conclusion that the true value of the measurand Y lies in the calculated
550 interval. The inference is statistical because it is based on data and because it is uncertain: it is derived by induction, not
551 deduction. If the conclusion is correct then the step of inference in any single measurement can be called 'successful'.
552 The relationship of the actual success rate of a measurement process to the implied figure, say 0.95, is described by the
553 concepts of accuracy and validity. The process is *accurate* if the success rate is 0.95, but it is *valid* if the success rate is
554 *at least* 0.95. From a practical point of view, validity is more important than accuracy because the nominal level has been
555 chosen to act as an *adequate minimum level of assurance* for the client. Provided that the implied rate is reached and the
556 intervals quoted are not unnecessarily long, it does not matter if the success rate is greater than the figure implied: the
557 only reason for seeking accuracy rather than validity is for the resulting intervals to be as short as possible, i.e., for the
558 measurement process to be as *efficient* as possible.

559 With regard to accuracy and validity, the GUM is vague about the practical meaning of 'expanded uncertainty': it
560 refers to "an interval ... with a coverage probability or level of confidence that corresponds in a realistic way with that
561 required" [1, 0.4], but it does not indicate what 'in a realistic way' actually means. And the literature surrounding the
562 revision of the GUM is silent about what can be expected of its 'numerical interval with a specified coverage probability'.
563 (In one sense, this is curious because science demands that its claims are falsifiable and that its procedures are meaningful.
564 On the other hand, we might expect there to be no performance criterion stated for a Bayesian system, because a Bayesian
565 analysis addresses someone's belief, not any observable physical reality. Provided that the person's belief is represented

566 accurately, a Bayesian method is regarded as being ‘correct by definition’. Such is the understanding of ‘validity’ apparent
 567 in the literature surrounding the BIPM’s proposed revision of the GUM, e.g., [2, 8.1.3].)

568 Notwithstanding this lack of acknowledgement, it seems reasonable to suggest that the principal idea of performance
 569 for the GUM procedure or its variants is found in the idea of success rate: it is obvious that a client who is quoted ‘95%
 570 uncertainty intervals’ in a set of unrelated problems can require approximately 95% (or more) of these intervals to contain
 571 the true values being studied. This, surely, is what the GUM means by ‘realistic’. So, our first performance characteristic
 572 is that the method will produce successful ‘95% uncertainty intervals’ at least 95 times out of 100 in a long sequence
 573 of different measurements. This is ensured if the method satisfies the stronger requirement of being successful at least
 574 95 times out of 100 when each individual measurement is repeated. Given this property, the method is then to generate
 575 narrow intervals, thus making the measurements as meaningful as possible. We will also consider the performance of
 576 99% intervals.

577 One point not often discussed is that failures are to occur symmetrically, so that approximately 2.5% of ‘95% intervals’
 578 lie fully above the true value and 2.5% lie fully below. This would mean that the procedure would be accurate with ‘one-
 579 tailed’ inferences as well as with intervals — as would be important in a context of conformance assessment, for example.
 580 Our Monte Carlo analysis below only involves the addition of variables with symmetric distributions. So symmetry is
 581 maintained and the performances of the one-sided inferences can be inferred from the results for the two-sided inferences.

582 5.1. Design of simulations

583 Monte Carlo simulations of simple measurements were carried out to compare the performances of the τ procedure
 584 and the GUM procedure. The basis of any such evaluation is the definition of a repeatable measurement scenario that gives
 585 meaning to a performance criterion. And to assess performance fairly, the measurement procedure must be simulated in a
 586 way that is consistent with the subsequent interpretation of the data. These considerations are not straightforward because
 587 Type B evaluation of uncertainty is informal and it is difficult to model an informal process.

588 In our simulations, the measurand is defined by the elementary function $\underline{Y} = \underline{X}_1 + \underline{X}_2$, with the uncertainty analysis in
 589 the measurement of \underline{X}_1 being of Type A and the uncertainty analysis in the measurement of \underline{X}_1 being of Type B. The two
 590 parts of the measurement are represented as follows.

- 591 1. The process of measuring \underline{X}_1 is understood to be the realizing of a normal random variable X_1 with mean \underline{X}_1
 592 and standard deviation σ_1 . The resulting measured value is x_1 . By the standard statistical principles of Type A
 593 evaluation with a sample of size n_1 , the figure u_1^2 is understood to be the realization (outcome) of an independent
 594 random variable U_1^2 with the distribution of $\sigma_1^2 \chi_{\nu_1}^2 / \nu_1$, where $\chi_{\nu_1}^2$ denotes a variable with the chi-square distribution
 595 with $\nu_1 = n_1 - 1$ degrees of freedom. So the measurement of \underline{X}_1 is defined by parameters \underline{X}_1 , σ_1 and ν_1 , the data
 596 generated are x_i and u_i , and the parameter ν_i is known. (These are standard concepts applicable when studying the
 597 mean of a normal distribution from a set of n_1 independent observations, e.g., [27, Ch. 5].)
- 598 2. The process of measuring \underline{X}_2 is understood to be the realizing of a random variable X_2 with mean \underline{X}_2 , standard de-
 599 viation σ_2 and known distributional form. The process generates an estimate x_2 and a figure of standard uncertainty
 600 u_2 that might itself be attributed a non-zero relative standard uncertainty δ_2 . In accordance with Recommendation
 601 INC-1, the figure u_2^2 is understood to be the realization of an independent random variable U_2^2 with mean σ_2^2 . The
 602 distribution of U_2^2 / σ_2^2 is governed by a single parameter λ_2 , which will relate to the figure δ_2 . In this way, the
 603 measurement of \underline{X}_2 is defined by (a) parameters \underline{X}_2 , σ_2 and λ_2 , (b) the form of the distribution of E_2 and (c) the
 604 implied thought-process leading to δ_2 . After some additional assumptions are made, it turns out that U_2^2 has the
 605 distribution of

$$\frac{\sigma_2^2}{\sqrt{\lambda_2}} \left(\lambda_2^{1/\sqrt{\log \lambda_2}} \right)^{Z_2} \quad \lambda_2 \geq 1 \quad (27)$$

606 where Z_2 has the standard normal distribution. (This reduces to the constant σ_2^2 when $\delta_2 = 0$, i.e., when $\lambda_2 = 1$.)
 607 Then $\delta_2 = \sqrt{(\lambda_2^{1/4} - 1)}$.

608 The question of how the ‘datum’ δ_2 fits such a description is not simple, because the practical process of Type B evaluation
 609 is informal. However, as is described in the Appendix, if we adhere to the GUM’s understanding of the meaning of δ_2
 610 then a suitable model, (27), emerges. In accordance with the GUM, δ_2 is used to represent the resulting ‘relative standard
 611 uncertainty’ in u_2 as an estimate of σ_2 . Furthermore, the concept of a ‘fiducial distribution for σ_2 ’ might be used to reflect
 612 the metrologist’s uncertainty about σ_2 after the observation of u_2 . The figure δ_2 will be the coefficient of variation of

613 this distribution, i.e., the standard deviation divided by the mean. Equation (27) and the subsequent use of the fiducial
 614 distribution might be called ‘the lognormal representation of Type B evaluation’.

615 As explained in the Appendix, the fiducial distribution for σ_2 is taken to be a lognormal distribution. The scale of this
 616 distribution is established by the requirement that U_2^2 be an unbiased estimator of σ_2^2 . This means that the distribution
 617 becomes defined by a single dispersion parameter $\lambda_2^{1/4}$. Consequently, the sampling distribution of U_2^2 that gave rise to
 618 this fiducial distribution is a lognormal distribution with dispersion parameter λ_2 . The parameter λ_2 is free, but it must
 619 lead to a realistic value of δ_2 .

620 So each measurement scenario is defined by (a) two unknown substantive parameters \underline{X}_1 and \underline{X}_2 , (b) two unknown
 621 variances σ_1^2 and σ_2^2 , (c) two simulation parameters ν_1 and λ_2 and (d) a known form of distribution for the Type B error
 622 E_2 . The parameter ν_1 is known and is available in the subsequent uncertainty analysis, and the parameter λ_2 is known
 623 implicitly through the value of a datum it generates, δ_2 . Without loss of generality, we can then set $\underline{X}_1 = 0$, $\underline{X}_2 = 0$ and
 624 $\sigma_1 = 1$, because the results of the performance comparison do not depend on parameters of location or on a common factor
 625 in the scales of E_1 and E_2 . Thus, the measurements considered correspond to different combinations of the parameters
 626 ν_1, σ_2 and λ_2 and different forms of distribution for E_2 .

627 We chose to study situations where the distribution of E_2 was double-exponential (Laplace), normal, isosceles tri-
 628 angular, uniform (rectangular) or arc-sine. These correspond to the raw figures of kurtosis $\gamma_i^* = 3, 0, -0.6, -1.2, -1.5$,
 629 respectively. For each combination of settings, the combined measurement was simulated 10^6 times and a record made of
 630 (a) the proportions of intervals from the τ and GUM procedures that contained the true value $\underline{Y} = 0$ and (b) the mean ratio
 631 of the width of the interval from the τ procedure to the width of the interval from the GUM procedure. The τ procedure
 632 was implemented in the way described in Section 4.7, where it uses δ_2 in (22). When it transpired that $\tau > 1$, (because σ_2 ,
 633 γ_2^* and δ_2 were all large), the coverage factor was found from the t-distribution with $1/\tau$ degrees of freedom. The GUM
 634 procedure was implemented as in Section 2.5, where it expresses δ_2 as a number of degrees of freedom $\nu_2 = 1/(2\delta_2^2)$ [1,
 635 G.3] conceptualized for use in the Welch-Satterthwaite formula. The effective number of degrees of freedom obtained
 636 from the Welch-Satterthwaite formula was kept fractional.

637 So the figure λ_2 is an artefact of our choice of a reasonable sampling model for the measurement of \underline{X}_2 . In contrast, δ_2
 638 is just a datum that results from this choice. However — because we have assumed that the metrologist forms the fiducial
 639 distribution in his or her thought process — this datum is a fixed function of λ_2 . As a result of this, the measurement
 640 scenarios studied involve a seemingly arbitrary choice of a parameter, λ_2 . We simulated measurements with λ_2 equal to
 641 1, 1.064, 1.2744, 2.4414, the resulting values of δ_2 being very close to 0, 0.125, 0.25 and 0.5.

642 (In the initial paper [6, Sec. 2.3], δ was interpreted as the halfwidth of a uniform distribution. Also, the GUM procedure
 643 takes the quantity $\Delta u_i/u_i$ seen in Section 2.5 to be the relative standard uncertainty of u_i [1, Equation G.3]. Taken together,
 644 these considerations imply that a fair use of the GUM procedure would have identified $\Delta u_i/u_i$ with $\delta_2/\sqrt{3}$ and that the
 645 associated number of degrees of freedom would be $\nu_2 = 3/(2\delta_2^2)$. However, $\Delta u_i/u_i$ was identified with δ_2 . This implies
 646 that there was an error in the comparisons of the methods in the initial paper.)

647 5.2. Results

648 The analyses were carried out for 95% and 99% intervals simultaneously. The results are shown in Tables 1 and 2,
 649 respectively. Each row relates to a single combination of ν_1, σ_2 and distributional form, and it contains results for the four
 650 settings of λ_2 . Here p_τ and p_G denote the percentages of intervals that were successful with the τ and GUM procedures,
 651 while \bar{r} denotes the mean of the ratio of the widths, which is just the mean value of the ratio of the coverage factor in
 652 the τ procedure to the coverage factor in the GUM procedure. With 10^6 trials in each simulation, the standard error in a
 653 percentage close to 95 or 99 is approximately 0.02 or 0.01. And the results indicate that the standard error in the estimate
 654 of the mean ratio of widths is less than 10^{-3} . Some results are highlighted to assist in interpretation of the tables. Values of
 655 p_τ less than 0.94 in Table 1 and less than 0.98 in Table 2 are struck through to indicate settings for which the τ procedure
 656 is perhaps too anti-conservative to be acceptable. For the other settings, width ratios of less than 0.9 are shown in bold.
 657 These indicate settings where (a) the τ procedure is acceptable and (b) the intervals it generates are more than 10% shorter
 658 than those obtained using the GUM procedure. Results for $\nu_1 = \infty$ are sufficient to show the behaviour of the method
 659 when a Type B error is dominant. Additional rows for $\sigma_2 = 0.1$ have been added to indicate that the τ procedure becomes
 660 exact as the Type A error becomes dominant, even when the Type B error has the arc-sine distribution.

ν_1	σ_2	dist. E_2	$\lambda = 1 \quad (\delta_2 = 0)$			$\lambda = 1.064 \quad (\delta_2 \approx 0.125)$			$\lambda = 1.2744 \quad (\delta_2 \approx 0.25)$			$\lambda = 2.4414 \quad (\delta_2 \approx 0.5)$		
			p_T	p_G	\bar{r}	p_T	p_G	\bar{r}	p_T	p_G	\bar{r}	p_T	p_G	\bar{r}
∞	100	Laplace	94.4	93.7	1.04	94.1	93.9	1.01	93.9	94.5	0.96	99.8	97.6	2.05
∞	100	normal	95.0	95.0	1.00	94.3	95.0	0.97	92.8	95.4	0.88	96.5	98.1	0.84
∞	100	isos.tri.	94.7	96.0	0.96	94.7	95.9	0.96	92.4	95.9	0.87	94.5	98.2	0.72
∞	100	uniform	95.0	100.0	0.84	96.8	99.3	0.89	94.2	97.9	0.86	92.2	98.7	0.63
∞	100	arc-sine	94.4	100.0	0.72	97.3	100.0	0.81	96.1	99.0	0.85	91.0	99.0	0.59
∞	10	Laplace	94.4	93.8	1.04	94.2	93.9	1.01	93.8	94.5	0.96	99.5	97.1	1.97
∞	10	normal	95.0	95.0	1.00	94.4	95.0	0.97	92.8	95.3	0.89	95.9	97.4	0.85
∞	10	isos.tri.	94.7	96.0	0.96	94.7	95.9	0.96	92.5	95.8	0.87	94.1	97.6	0.74
∞	10	uniform	95.4	100.0	0.85	96.7	99.1	0.90	94.2	97.8	0.86	91.9	98.0	0.64
∞	10	arc-sine	92.8	100.0	0.73	97.1	99.9	0.82	96.1	98.9	0.85	90.8	98.3	0.61
8	3.0	Laplace	94.5	94.0	1.03	94.3	94.1	1.01	94.0	94.4	0.97	97.7	95.4	1.61
8	3.0	normal	95.0	95.0	1.00	94.5	95.0	0.98	93.2	95.1	0.91	94.4	95.5	0.89
8	3.0	isos.tri.	95.2	95.8	0.98	94.9	95.7	0.97	93.1	95.6	0.90	93.0	95.4	0.81
8	3.0	uniform	95.9	98.4	0.92	96.3	97.8	0.94	94.4	97.0	0.89	91.9	95.8	0.74
8	3.0	arc-sine	95.2	99.3	0.86	96.7	98.9	0.90	95.5	97.9	0.88	91.5	96.1	0.71
8	1.0	Laplace	94.9	94.7	1.01	94.9	94.8	1.00	94.8	95.0	0.99	96.1	95.1	1.15
8	1.0	normal	94.9	94.9	1.00	94.8	95.0	0.99	94.5	95.2	0.97	94.9	95.3	0.97
8	1.0	isos.tri.	95.0	95.1	1.00	94.8	95.1	0.99	94.5	95.4	0.96	94.6	95.3	0.94
8	1.0	uniform	95.2	95.4	1.00	95.1	95.5	0.99	94.6	95.6	0.96	94.4	95.5	0.92
8	1.0	arc-sine	95.4	95.6	0.99	95.2	95.6	0.98	94.8	95.7	0.96	94.3	95.7	0.90
8	0.5	Laplace	94.8	94.7	1.00	94.9	94.8	1.00	94.9	95.0	1.00	95.7	95.3	1.04
8	0.5	normal	94.8	94.8	1.00	94.8	94.8	1.00	94.7	94.9	0.99	95.2	95.3	0.99
8	0.5	isos.tri.	94.8	94.8	1.00	94.8	94.8	1.00	94.7	94.9	0.99	95.1	95.3	0.99
8	0.5	uniform	94.8	94.8	1.00	94.8	94.8	1.00	94.7	95.0	0.99	95.0	95.4	0.98
8	0.5	arc-sine	94.8	94.8	1.00	94.8	94.9	1.00	94.8	95.1	0.99	94.9	95.3	0.97
8	0.1	arc-sine	95.0	95.0	1.00	95.0	95.0	1.00	95.0	95.0	1.00	95.0	95.0	1.00
4	3.0	Laplace	94.5	94.0	1.03	94.3	94.1	1.01	94.1	94.6	0.97	98.0	95.8	1.63
4	3.0	normal	95.0	95.0	1.00	94.5	95.0	0.98	93.3	95.3	0.91	94.8	95.9	0.89
4	3.0	isos.tri.	95.3	95.8	0.98	94.8	95.7	0.97	93.2	95.7	0.90	93.5	96.0	0.81
4	3.0	uniform	95.9	98.3	0.93	96.3	97.9	0.94	94.5	97.1	0.89	92.3	96.4	0.74
4	3.0	arc-sine	94.9	99.3	0.87	96.6	98.8	0.90	95.6	98.0	0.88	92.0	96.8	0.70
4	1.0	Laplace	94.8	94.5	1.01	94.8	94.7	1.01	94.8	95.1	0.99	97.0	95.8	1.19
4	1.0	normal	94.7	94.7	1.00	94.6	94.8	0.99	94.3	95.2	0.96	95.5	95.9	0.96
4	1.0	isos.tri.	94.8	94.8	1.00	94.6	95.0	0.99	94.3	95.3	0.96	95.1	96.0	0.93
4	1.0	uniform	94.8	95.0	0.99	94.7	95.2	0.98	94.4	95.6	0.95	94.7	96.2	0.90
4	1.0	arc-sine	94.8	95.2	0.99	94.7	95.3	0.98	94.4	95.7	0.95	94.4	96.3	0.89
4	0.5	Laplace	94.3	94.1	1.00	94.3	94.3	1.00	94.5	94.6	1.00	96.2	95.5	1.05
4	0.5	normal	94.1	94.1	1.00	94.2	94.3	1.00	94.3	94.7	0.99	95.3	95.5	0.99
4	0.5	isos.tri.	94.1	94.1	1.00	94.2	94.3	1.00	94.2	94.6	0.99	95.0	95.5	0.98
4	0.5	uniform	94.1	94.2	1.00	94.2	94.3	1.00	94.2	94.6	0.99	94.8	95.5	0.97
4	0.5	arc-sine	94.2	94.2	1.00	94.1	94.3	1.00	94.2	94.7	0.99	94.6	95.5	0.96
4	0.1	arc-sine	94.8	94.8	1.00	94.8	94.8	1.00	94.8	94.8	1.00	94.8	94.9	1.00
2	3.0	Laplace	94.5	94.0	1.03	94.4	94.2	1.01	94.2	94.7	0.97	98.6	96.4	1.67
2	3.0	normal	95.0	95.0	1.00	94.5	95.1	0.97	93.4	95.4	0.91	95.6	96.7	0.89
2	3.0	isos.tri.	95.3	95.8	0.98	94.9	95.8	0.97	93.3	95.8	0.90	94.3	96.9	0.80
2	3.0	uniform	95.6	98.3	0.93	96.2	97.8	0.94	94.5	97.2	0.88	93.2	97.4	0.73
2	3.0	arc-sine	94.0	99.3	0.87	96.2	98.8	0.90	95.5	98.0	0.88	92.8	97.7	0.69
2	1.0	Laplace	94.5	94.1	1.02	94.6	94.4	1.01	94.6	95.0	0.98	98.1	96.6	1.26
2	1.0	normal	94.1	94.1	1.00	94.0	94.4	0.99	93.8	95.0	0.95	96.1	96.8	0.95
2	1.0	isos.tri.	94.0	94.2	1.00	93.9	94.4	0.98	93.7	95.1	0.95	95.4	96.8	0.91
2	1.0	uniform	93.7	94.3	0.99	93.8	94.6	0.98	93.6	95.3	0.94	94.7	97.0	0.87
2	1.0	arc-sine	93.2	94.4	0.98	93.6	94.7	0.97	93.6	95.4	0.94	94.3	97.0	0.86
2	0.5	Laplace	92.7	92.5	1.01	92.9	92.8	1.00	93.3	93.5	0.99	97.0	95.5	1.10
2	0.5	normal	92.5	92.4	1.00	92.5	92.7	0.99	92.7	93.4	0.98	95.0	95.5	0.98
2	0.5	isos.tri.	92.4	92.4	1.00	92.5	92.7	0.99	92.6	93.4	0.98	94.5	95.5	0.96
2	0.5	uniform	92.2	92.4	0.99	92.3	92.7	0.99	92.5	93.4	0.97	94.0	95.6	0.94
2	0.5	arc-sine	92.1	92.4	0.99	92.2	92.7	0.99	92.4	93.4	0.97	93.7	95.5	0.94
2	0.1	arc-sine	93.8	93.8	1.00	93.8	93.9	1.00	93.9	94.0	1.00	94.1	94.3	1.00

Table 1: Performance results of 95% intervals when measuring $\underline{Y} = \underline{X}_1 + \underline{X}_2$ where $E_1 \equiv X_1 - \underline{X}_1$ is a Type A error and $E_2 \equiv X_2 - \underline{X}_2$ is a Type B error

ν_1	σ_2	dist. E_2	$\lambda = 1 \quad (\delta_2 = 0)$			$\lambda = 1.064 \quad (\delta_2 \approx 0.125)$			$\lambda = 1.2744 \quad (\delta_2 \approx 0.25)$			$\lambda = 2.4414 \quad (\delta_2 \approx 0.5)$		
			p_T	p_G	\bar{r}	p_T	p_G	\bar{r}	p_T	p_G	\bar{r}	p_T	p_G	\bar{r}
∞	100	Laplace	97.9	97.4	1.06	97.8	97.6	1.02	97.9	98.3	0.93	100.0	99.9	3.47
∞	100	normal	99.0	99.0	1.00	98.6	99.0	0.95	97.8	99.2	0.82	99.8	100.0	0.74
∞	100	isos.tri.	99.4	100.0	0.88	99.5	99.8	0.93	98.2	99.7	0.80	99.4	100.0	0.56
∞	100	uniform	99.1	100.0	0.67	99.5	100.0	0.76	99.2	99.9	0.78	98.8	100.0	0.44
∞	100	arc-sine	96.4	100.0	0.55	98.6	100.0	0.63	99.7	100.0	0.77	98.4	100.0	0.39
∞	10	Laplace	98.0	97.4	1.06	97.8	97.7	1.02	97.8	98.3	0.94	100.0	99.7	3.25
∞	10	normal	99.0	99.0	1.00	98.7	99.0	0.95	97.8	99.2	0.82	99.5	99.8	0.75
∞	10	isos.tri.	99.3	100.0	0.88	99.5	99.8	0.93	98.3	99.7	0.80	99.1	99.8	0.58
∞	10	uniform	98.1	100.0	0.68	99.4	100.0	0.76	99.2	99.9	0.78	98.5	99.9	0.46
∞	10	arc-sine	93.3	100.0	0.56	98.6	100.0	0.64	99.7	100.0	0.77	98.1	99.9	0.42
8	3.0	Laplace	98.0	97.6	1.05	97.9	97.8	1.02	97.9	98.2	0.95	99.5	98.8	2.33
8	3.0	normal	99.0	99.0	1.00	98.7	99.0	0.96	98.1	99.1	0.86	98.7	99.1	0.82
8	3.0	isos.tri.	99.3	99.8	0.93	99.4	99.6	0.95	98.5	99.5	0.84	98.4	99.2	0.70
8	3.0	uniform	98.4	100.0	0.79	99.4	99.9	0.85	99.2	99.8	0.83	98.2	99.4	0.60
8	3.0	arc-sine	96.6	100.0	0.71	98.9	100.0	0.76	99.5	99.9	0.82	98.2	99.5	0.56
8	1.0	Laplace	98.6	98.4	1.02	98.6	98.5	1.01	98.6	98.7	0.98	99.2	98.9	1.30
8	1.0	normal	98.9	98.9	1.00	98.9	99.0	0.99	98.8	99.1	0.95	99.0	99.1	0.95
8	1.0	isos.tri.	99.0	99.1	1.00	99.0	99.1	0.98	98.8	99.2	0.94	99.0	99.2	0.90
8	1.0	uniform	99.1	99.3	0.99	99.1	99.3	0.98	98.9	99.3	0.94	98.9	99.3	0.86
8	1.0	arc-sine	99.1	99.3	0.99	99.1	99.3	0.97	99.0	99.4	0.93	98.9	99.4	0.85
8	0.5	Laplace	98.8	98.7	1.01	98.8	98.8	1.00	98.9	98.9	1.00	99.3	99.1	1.06
8	0.5	normal	98.8	98.8	1.00	98.8	98.9	1.00	98.8	98.9	0.99	99.1	99.2	0.99
8	0.5	isos.tri.	98.8	98.8	1.00	98.8	98.9	1.00	98.8	99.0	0.99	99.0	99.2	0.98
8	0.5	uniform	98.8	98.8	1.00	98.8	98.9	1.00	98.8	99.0	0.99	99.0	99.2	0.96
8	0.5	arc-sine	98.8	98.9	1.00	98.8	98.9	1.00	98.9	99.0	0.99	99.0	99.2	0.96
8	0.1	arc-sine	99.0	99.0	1.00	99.0	99.0	1.00	99.0	99.0	1.00	99.0	99.0	1.00
4	3.0	Laplace	98.0	97.6	1.05	98.0	97.8	1.02	97.9	98.3	0.95	99.7	99.1	2.39
4	3.0	normal	99.0	99.0	1.00	98.7	99.0	0.96	98.1	99.2	0.86	99.0	99.3	0.82
4	3.0	isos.tri.	99.3	99.8	0.94	99.4	99.6	0.95	98.5	99.6	0.84	98.8	99.5	0.69
4	3.0	uniform	98.2	100.0	0.82	99.4	99.9	0.86	99.2	99.8	0.82	98.6	99.6	0.59
4	3.0	arc-sine	96.4	100.0	0.74	98.7	100.0	0.79	99.5	99.9	0.82	98.5	99.7	0.55
4	1.0	Laplace	98.6	98.3	1.02	98.6	98.5	1.01	98.7	98.8	0.98	99.6	99.3	1.38
4	1.0	normal	98.8	98.7	1.00	98.7	98.9	0.99	98.6	99.1	0.94	99.3	99.4	0.93
4	1.0	isos.tri.	98.8	98.9	1.00	98.7	99.0	0.98	98.6	99.2	0.93	99.2	99.5	0.88
4	1.0	uniform	98.7	99.0	0.99	98.8	99.1	0.97	98.7	99.3	0.93	99.0	99.5	0.84
4	1.0	arc-sine	98.5	99.1	0.98	98.6	99.2	0.97	98.7	99.3	0.92	98.9	99.6	0.82
4	0.5	Laplace	98.4	98.2	1.01	98.4	98.4	1.00	98.6	98.7	0.99	99.5	99.2	1.10
4	0.5	normal	98.3	98.3	1.00	98.3	98.4	1.00	98.4	98.7	0.98	99.1	99.2	0.98
4	0.5	isos.tri.	98.3	98.3	1.00	98.3	98.4	0.99	98.4	98.7	0.98	99.0	99.2	0.96
4	0.5	uniform	98.2	98.3	1.00	98.3	98.4	0.99	98.4	98.7	0.98	98.9	99.3	0.95
4	0.5	arc-sine	98.2	98.3	1.00	98.3	98.4	0.99	98.3	98.7	0.98	98.8	99.2	0.94
4	0.1	arc-sine	98.8	98.8	1.00	98.8	98.8	1.00	98.8	98.8	1.00	98.8	98.9	1.00
2	3.0	Laplace	98.1	97.6	1.05	98.0	97.9	1.02	98.1	98.4	0.95	99.9	99.5	2.50
2	3.0	normal	99.0	99.0	1.00	98.7	99.0	0.96	98.2	99.3	0.85	99.4	99.7	0.81
2	3.0	isos.tri.	99.2	99.8	0.95	99.3	99.6	0.95	98.5	99.6	0.84	99.2	99.8	0.68
2	3.0	uniform	97.8	100.0	0.83	99.2	99.9	0.86	99.1	99.8	0.82	98.9	99.9	0.58
2	3.0	arc-sine	94.9	100.0	0.76	98.2	100.0	0.80	99.4	99.9	0.81	98.8	99.9	0.54
2	1.0	Laplace	98.4	98.1	1.03	98.4	98.3	1.01	98.5	98.7	0.97	99.9	99.6	1.55
2	1.0	normal	98.3	98.3	1.00	98.3	98.5	0.98	98.1	99.0	0.93	99.5	99.7	0.91
2	1.0	isos.tri.	98.2	98.5	0.99	98.3	98.6	0.97	98.1	99.0	0.92	99.2	99.7	0.85
2	1.0	uniform	97.4	98.6	0.97	97.9	98.8	0.96	98.1	99.2	0.91	98.9	99.7	0.80
2	1.0	arc-sine	96.7	98.7	0.95	97.4	98.8	0.94	98.1	99.2	0.90	98.7	99.7	0.77
2	0.5	Laplace	97.2	96.9	1.01	97.4	97.2	1.00	97.7	97.9	0.99	99.7	99.3	1.21
2	0.5	normal	97.0	96.9	1.00	97.0	97.2	0.99	97.2	97.9	0.97	99.0	99.3	0.96
2	0.5	isos.tri.	96.8	96.9	1.00	96.9	97.2	0.99	97.0	97.9	0.96	98.7	99.3	0.93
2	0.5	uniform	96.5	96.9	0.99	96.7	97.2	0.98	97.0	97.9	0.96	98.3	99.3	0.91
2	0.5	arc-sine	96.3	96.9	0.98	96.5	97.2	0.98	96.9	97.9	0.96	98.0	99.3	0.90
2	0.1	arc-sine	97.6	97.7	1.00	97.7	97.7	1.00	97.8	97.8	1.00	98.0	98.3	0.99

Table 2: Performance results of 99% intervals when measuring $Y = \underline{X}_1 + \underline{X}_2$ where $E_1 \equiv X_1 - \underline{X}_1$ is a Type A error and $E_2 \equiv X_2 - \underline{X}_2$ is a Type B error

665 The measurements simulated are simplistic, because in practice there will be more than two contributions. Therefore,
666 there is little to be gained by tuning the method to address situations where the figure is struck through. Instead, we use
667 the results in Tables 1 and 2 to suggest some general principles.

- 668 1. The τ procedure is well-behaved when the problem is well-behaved, i.e., when the problem does not involve extreme
669 settings of multiple factors.
- 670 2. The τ procedure is hardly ever conservative, but the GUM procedure is often conservative when a Type B error is
671 influential. Accordingly, the τ procedure leads to shorter intervals. The reduction in length can be substantial when
672 a single Type B error is dominant.
- 673 3. It is possible to construct a scenario where the intervals from the τ procedure are longer than those from the GUM
674 procedure, but such a situation would be extreme. Thus, for example, the method might not be advantageous when
675 a significant component of error is attributed a Laplace distribution in a Type B evaluation.
- 676 4. The τ procedure deals adequately with the possibility that the metrologist is uncertain about the standard deviation
677 to associate with a Type B evaluation of error: results are acceptable for values of δ up to 0.5.
- 678 5. The use of an arc-sine distribution for a significant component of error can lead to surprising behaviour in methods
679 based on ‘exact’ probability calculations. This is especially the case with 99% intervals, where the natural quantile
680 is close to the point of discontinuity.
- 681 6. Practical measurement problems involve more than two contributions. The averaging effect of the central-limit
682 theorem in those problems will assist both procedures.

683 The results seen in Tables 1 and 2 are not perfect — but perfection is unattainable in this difficult task. The results suggest
684 that, as well as being more satisfactory theoretically, the τ procedure offers benefit in terms of performance.

685 6. Conclusion

686 This paper has described a system of uncertainty analysis that follows classical statistical principles. The method is
687 built on the elementary ideas that (i) measurement is the estimation of a true value, (ii) error is unavoidable and (iii) the
688 parent population of a component of error is describable by a probability distribution. The distributions of components can
689 then be summarized by their means and central moments. The methodology is based around a corrected understanding of
690 CIPM Recommendation INC-1 (1980), which is regarded as a foundation of the GUM. It seeks to avoid the controversial
691 Bayesian idea of probability as ‘belief about a constant’, which is the key feature of the approach currently being sought
692 and promoted by the BIPM. Consequently, logical inconsistencies associated with the idea that ‘information means belief’
693 are avoided [14, 28] and performance criteria for the method remain both clear and agreeable. It is also consistent with
694 how others outside the metrology community have interpreted the GUM, e.g., [22, 23, 24].

695 In Type A evaluation of measurement uncertainty, the method follows the GUM. In Type B evaluation, the method
696 replaces the GUM’s concept of an artificial non-negative number of degrees of freedom by the classical concept of the
697 kurtosis of the distribution, which could be either positive or negative. Consequently, appropriate propagation of the
698 variance-estimates in Type A analysis and the variance-estimates and kurtoses in Type B analysis leads to a system
699 wherein the stated measurement uncertainty can legitimately be smaller than with the procedure of the GUM.

700 The method may be described as neo-classical. It utilizes frequentist principles whilst adhering to the correct inter-
701 pretation of the pragmatic Recommendation INC-1. The corresponding practical procedure exhibits *internal consistency*
702 and *transferability*, and it could be extended to approach *universality*. It is as simple as the procedure of the GUM, and
703 it has been examined for *validity* and *efficiency* in simple problems. In any practical method of data analysis, there is
704 tension between level of performance and simplicity, so further discussion of practical requirements could lead to further
705 refinement.

706 Any candidate procedure for the evaluation of measurement uncertainty should be subject to empirical examination,
707 presumably by the simulation of meaningful measurements. This requires a model for the metrologist’s process of Type B
708 evaluation of uncertainty, in particular for the generation of a statement such as “the standard uncertainty u_i is reliable to
709 100 $\delta\%$ ”. This paper has presented a simple method of simulation in which this statement can be given the interpretation
710 found for it in the GUM. Both the new procedure of uncertainty analysis and this technique of performance assessment
711 are offered as tools in the development of a sound and practical system for the evaluation of uncertainty in measurement.

712 **Appendix: A way of understanding and modelling Type B evaluation**

713 This Appendix describes the development of (20) and, hence, (22) as a means of incorporating uncertainty about the
 714 standard deviation of a Type B error. This equation enables the non-normality of an error and uncertainty about its scale
 715 to be encapsulated in a single figure of effective kurtosis, for subsequent representation as an auxiliary figure τ_i . At the
 716 same time, the material provides a basis for the simulation of measurements involving Type B evaluations of uncertainty,
 717 as would be required in an empirical examination of any proposed method of combining Type A and Type B components.
 718 Such simulations are described in Section 5.1.

719 The analysis here mixes two different views of probability, and it is informal. It involves the frequentist of probability,
 720 which is advocated in this paper, and the concept of fiducial probability, which is much less well known. For clarity, we
 721 will suppress the subscript i .

722 *Fiducial distribution for a parameter*

723 Following Recommendation INC-1, we interpret a standard uncertainty u obtained in Type B evaluation to be an
 724 estimate of a ‘correct’ standard deviation σ . Imagine that u is seen as being “reliable to 100 $\delta\%$ ”. In the GUM, such a
 725 statement is taken to mean that δ is the relative standard uncertainty associated with u [1, G.4.2, H.1.6]. So, if the GUM is
 726 encouraging the analyst to think in terms of a ‘probability distribution for σ ’ located around u then this distribution would
 727 have standard deviation equal to 100 $\delta\% \times u$. Such a distribution might be formed using the idea of ‘fiducial inference’,
 728 where the standard sampling distribution of an estimator dependent on a parameter is ‘inverted’ to form the fiducial
 729 distribution of the parameter given the ensuing estimate. Here, we propose a reasonable form for the fiducial distribution,
 730 and then we invert the inversion to recover the corresponding sampling distribution of the underlying variance estimator
 731 U^2 . We then identify the scale factor that makes U^2 an unbiased estimator of σ^2 . Then we will have constructed a model
 732 of the measurement procedure in which u^2 is an unbiased estimate of σ^2 , as is required in the propagation of variance.
 733 This model will enable us to take into account ‘fiducial’ uncertainty in u when incorporating the stated figure of kurtosis
 734 γ^* .

735 (Fiducial inference is similar to Bayesian inference in as much as it involves constructing a probability distribution
 736 for a fixed parameter. However, it does not involve the controversial idea of a prior distribution describing ‘prior belief’
 737 about the parameter, so it could be said to be more objective than Bayesian inference. For example of fiducial methods in
 738 metrology, see work of Hannig, Iyer and Wang [29, 30, 31].)

739 *Lognormal distribution*

740 We propose taking the ‘fiducial distribution’ of σ to be a (two-parameter) *lognormal* distribution, i.e., the distribution
 741 of the exponential of a normal variable. If the random variable Z has the standard normal distribution then (a) the variable
 742 $\zeta + Z\psi$ has the normal distribution with mean ζ and variance ψ^2 and (b) the variable

$$Y \equiv \exp(\zeta + Z\psi) = \exp(\zeta)\exp(Z\psi) = \exp(\zeta)\exp(\psi)^Z$$

743 has a lognormal distribution with r th moment about the origin [32, 14.7]

$$\mathcal{E}[Y^r] = \exp(r\zeta) \omega^{r^2/2} \quad \omega \equiv \exp(\psi^2).$$

744 So the mean and coefficient of variation of Y are

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}[Y] &= \exp(\zeta) \sqrt{\omega} \\ \text{c.v.}[Y] &\equiv \frac{\sqrt{\text{var}[Y]}}{\mathcal{E}[Y]} = \sqrt{\omega - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

745 The lognormal distribution is usually parametrized differently, but here we will say that Y has the lognormal distribu-
 746 tion with parameters ζ and ω . We will denote such a variable by $\text{LN}(\zeta, \omega)$ and we will write $Y \stackrel{\text{dist}}{=} \text{LN}(\zeta, \omega)$ where $\stackrel{\text{dist}}{=}$
 747 means “is equal in distribution to” or “has the same distribution as”. The parameter ζ acts as a scale parameter through
 748 the factor $\exp(\zeta)$, while the parameter ω relates to the relative dispersion (and shape). In this context, the symbols ζ and
 749 ω are standard. Our presentation here is such that ζ is always zero and ω has one of two values, λ and $\phi \equiv \lambda^{1/4}$.

750 *Bringing the ideas together*

751 Now, in accordance with Recommendation INC-1, we envisage u^2 being the realization of a random variable U^2 with
 752 mean σ^2 . Suppose that the distribution of U^2 is lognormal with dispersion parameter λ . Then $U^2 \stackrel{\text{dist}}{=} \sigma^2 \text{LN}(0, \lambda) / \sqrt{\lambda}$,
 753 which implies that

$$\frac{U}{\sigma} \stackrel{\text{dist}}{=} \frac{\text{LN}(0, \phi)}{\phi} \stackrel{\text{dist}}{=} \frac{1}{\phi \text{LN}(0, \phi)} \quad \phi \equiv \lambda^{1/4}.$$

754 This means that the fiducial distribution attributed to σ/u after observation of u would be the distribution of $\phi \text{LN}(0, \phi)$,
 755 which has coefficient of variation $\sqrt{\phi - 1}$. Thus, $\delta = \sqrt{\phi - 1}$ and $\phi = 1 + \delta^2$. The simulation can be carried out easily by
 756 recognizing that, equivalently,

$$U^2 \stackrel{\text{dist}}{=} \begin{cases} \sigma^2 & \lambda = 1 \\ \frac{\sigma^2}{\sqrt{\lambda}} \left(\lambda^{1/\sqrt{\log \lambda}} \right)^Z & \lambda > 1. \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

757 In summary, if we regard Type B evaluation as the formation of a fiducial distribution for σ and interpret the idea that
 758 “ u is reliable to $100\delta\%$ ” to mean that this distribution has coefficient of variation δ then we can consider the sampling
 759 distribution of U^2 to be the distribution of $\sigma^2 \sqrt{\lambda} \text{LN}(0, \lambda)$ where $\lambda = (1 + \delta^2)^4$ or, equivalently, to be the distribution
 760 of the variable on the right-hand side of (28). Also, we can consider the ensuing fiducial distribution of σ/u to be the
 761 distribution of $\phi \text{LN}(0, \phi)$ where $\phi = 1 + \delta^2$.

762 *Adjustment to the figure of kurtosis*

763 In the fiducial thought process, the parameter σ is being seen as a distributed quantity. So the original moments
 764 recorded for the error E might be adjusted to represent this ‘broadening’ of the distribution of E . For the correct propaga-
 765 tion of variance, it is important that we retain u^2 as an unbiased figure of variance. So our attention is placed on calculating
 766 an effective fourth moment (about the origin) and representing this in a new figure of kurtosis, γ . We consider what the
 767 fourth moment of the error would be in terms of u , γ^* and δ if the error was drawn from a distribution where the scale
 768 factor σ was itself distributed in the fiducial sense.

769 Let V be a variable with the distribution of E conditional on u being exact, and let W be an independent variable with
 770 the fiducial distribution of σ/u . The distribution of the product VW represents a distribution attributable to E when we
 771 account for error in u , so we wish to find the fourth moment of VW . The variable V has mean zero, so its fourth moment
 772 is the fourth central moment $(3 + \gamma^*)u^4$. Also, W has the distribution of $\phi \text{LN}(0, \phi)$, so its fourth moment is $\mathcal{E}[W^4] = \phi^{12}$.
 773 The r th moment (about the origin) of the product of two independent variables is the product of the r th moments of the
 774 individual variables, so the fourth moment of VW is

$$\mathcal{E}[(VW)^4] = \phi^{12}(\gamma^* + 3)u^4 = (1 + \delta^2)^{12}(\gamma^* + 3)u^4.$$

Because VW has mean zero, this must also be the fourth central moment μ_4 . Given that u^2 remains the stated figure of
 variance, the corresponding value of kurtosis is $\mu_4/u^4 - 3$, which is

$$\gamma = (1 + \delta^2)^{12}(\gamma^* + 3) - 3.$$

775 When we reapply the subscript, we obtain (20). (There are no probability distributions with kurtosis less than -2 , so this
 776 equation implies that $\gamma \geq \gamma^*$.)

777 *Discussion*

778 The adjustment is obtained by mixing the frequentist and fiducial paradigms of inference, but the corresponding ideas
 779 are not central to the interpretation of the result. So the adjustment is to be judged on the basis of practicality and per-
 780 formance, not theoretical consistency. Advocates of fiducial methods often evaluate them using frequentist performance
 781 criteria anyway, so this method of analysis can be seen as a use, not an abuse, of the fiducial idea. The analysis begins
 782 with the metrologist’s statement “ u_i is reliable to $100\delta\%$ ” and the fact that this statement says nothing about asymmetry.
 783 Consequently, we look for a fiducial distribution of σ that would be broadly symmetric, notwithstanding the constraint
 784 that σ is non-negative. A lognormal distribution appears suitable.

785 As suggested in the text, the concept of being unsure about a hypothetical standard deviation is questionable. So
 786 the theoretical relevance of this adjustment is unclear. However, there is a by-product of this analysis: the methodology
 787 suggests a reasonable and simple way of simulating the thought process of the metrologist in a Type B evaluation. This
 788 enables an examination of the performance of a system of uncertainty analysis. Such a methodology has been lacking in
 789 the literature, especially in the literature surrounding the revision of the GUM.

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